

Included Papers and Metadata(n=53)

ID	Title	Year	Main Context	Primary Focus
1	Efficient Anomaly Detection for Smart Hospital IoT Systems	2021	Smart hospital	Event and intrusion detection
2	Trustworthy Intrusion Detection in E-Healthcare Systems	2021	E-healthcare IoT	Intrusion detection
3	An Adaptive Intrusion Detection System in the Internet of Medical Things Using Fuzzy-Based Learning	2023	IoMT	Adaptive intrusion detection
4	Detection of Middlebox-Based Attacks in Healthcare Internet of Things Using Multiple Machine Learning Models	2022	Healthcare IoT	Middlebox attack detection
5	Intrusion Detection and Real-Time Adaptive Security in Medical IoT Using Machine Learning and Communicating Concurrent Processes	2025	Medical IoT CPS	Real-time adaptive IDS
6	MEDIotWALL: Securing Smart Healthcare Environments Through IoT Firewalls	2025	Smart healthcare operations	Device and network defense
7	XAI-XGBoost: an innovative explainable intrusion detection approach for securing internet of medical things systems	2025	IoMT	Explainable intrusion detection
8	Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning for Internet of Medical Things Under Edge Computing	2023	IoMT and edge healthcare	Privacy-preserving learning
9	FIDChain: Federated Intrusion Detection System for Healthcare IoT	2022	Healthcare IoT	Privacy-preserving intrusion detection
10	BFLIDS: Blockchain-Driven Federated Learning for Intrusion Detection in IoMT Networks	2024	IoMT	Secure and scalable IDS
11	SA-FLIDS: secure and authenticated federated learning-based intelligent network intrusion detection system for smart healthcare	2024	Fog-IoMT	Secure federated NIDS
12	FedMedSecure: federated few-shot learning with cross-attention mechanisms and explainable AI for collaborative healthcare cybersecurity	2025	Collaborative healthcare cybersecurity	Privacy, few-shot learning, XAI
13	EnDuSecFed: an ensemble approach for privacy preserving Federated Learning with dual-security framework for sustainable healthcare	2026	Sustainable healthcare FL	Secure federated learning
14	A Laboratory-Based Federated Learning Deployment on Real Devices for ECG-Based Clinical Decision Support Systems	2025	ECG and CDSS IoMT	Real-device FL deployment
15	Secure edge-based IoMT framework for ICU monitoring with TinyML and post-quantum cryptography	2025	ICU IoMT	Real-time anomaly detection and secure communication
16	Edge-AI integrated secure wireless IoT architecture for real time healthcare monitoring and federated anomaly detection	2026	Smart healthcare monitoring	Low-latency secure anomaly detection
17	Improved Wireless Medical Cyber-Physical System (IWMCPs) Based on Machine Learning	2023	Medical cyber-physical systems	Attack detection in MCPs
18	A Lightweight Mutual Authentication and Privacy-preservation Scheme for Intelligent Wearable Devices in Industrial-CPS	2021	Wearable I-CPS	Authentication and privacy preservation
19	Secure data authentication and access control protocol for industrial healthcare system	2023	E-health and IoMT	Secure authentication and access control
20	An Improved Lightweight User Authentication Scheme for the Internet of Medical Things	2023	IoMT authentication	User and gateway authentication
21	Lightweight Privacy-Preserving Data Sharing Scheme for Internet of Medical Things	2021	IoMT cloud sharing	Privacy-preserving data sharing
22	A secure authentication protocol for remote patient monitoring in an internet-of-medical-things environment	2024	IoMT remote patient monitoring	Privacy-preserving authentication
23	A lightweight and secure authentication and privacy protection scheme for internet of medical things	2025	IoMT authentication	Authentication and privacy protection
24	A lightweight privacy preservation authentication protocol for IoMT using ECC based blind signature	2025	IoMT authentication	Lightweight privacy-preserving authentication
25	A Lightweight and Privacy-Preserving Authentication Protocol for IoT-Based Healthcare	2023	Healthcare IoT WSN	Privacy-preserving authentication
26	A secure and privacy preserved data aggregation scheme in IoMT	2024	IoMT edge/fog	Privacy-preserving aggregation
27	Secure and lightweight privacy preserving Internet of things integration for remote patient monitoring	2022	Remote patient monitoring	Secure IoT-health integration
28	An Intrusion Detection System for Internet of Medical Things	2020	IoMT	Intrusion detection
29	Security of Things Intrusion Detection System for Smart Healthcare	2021	Smart healthcare	Intrusion detection
30	A Multi-View Attention-Based Deep Learning Framework for Malware Detection in Smart Healthcare Systems	2022	Smart healthcare	Malware detection
31	A Fuzzy-Based Duo-Secure Multi-Modal Framework for IoMT Anomaly Detection	2023	IoMT	Anomaly detection
32	Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning-Based Intrusion Detection System for IoHT Devices	2025	IoHT	Privacy-preserving IDS

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ID	Title	Year	Main Context	Primary Focus
33	Deep Learning-Driven Anomaly Detection for IoMT-Based Smart Healthcare Systems	2024	IoMT-based smart healthcare	Anomaly detection
34	Guarding Digital Health: Deep Learning for Attack Detection in Medical IoT	2024	Medical IoT	Attack detection
35	An Explainable AI Approach for Interpretable Cross-Layer Intrusion Detection in Internet of Medical Things	2025	IoMT	Interpretable cross-layer IDS
36	A Deep Reinforcement Learning-Based Robust Intrusion Detection System for Securing IoMT Healthcare Networks	2025	IoMT healthcare networks	Robust intrusion detection
37	Feature Efficiency in IoMT Security: A Comprehensive Framework for Threat Detection with DNN and ML	2025	IoMT security	Threat detection
38	Towards Advanced AI-Based Solutions for Securing IoMT in Smart Health Information Systems	2026	Smart health information systems	AI-based IoMT security
39	A Two-Stage Federated Learning Framework for Human Activity and Anomaly Detection in IoMT	2025	IoMT	Human activity and anomaly detection
40	Blockchain-integrated security for real-time patient monitoring in the internet of medical things using federated learning	2023	Real-time patient monitoring in IoMT	Secure collaborative monitoring
41	Hierarchical federated learning based anomaly detection using digital twins for smart healthcare	2021	Smart healthcare	Anomaly detection
42	Advancing hospital healthcare: achieving IoT-based secure health monitoring through multilayer machine learning	2025	Hospital healthcare	Secure health monitoring
43	Dew-cloud-based hierarchical federated learning for intrusion detection in IoMT	2023	IoMT	Intrusion detection
44	Efficient cyber attack detection on the internet of medical things-smart environment based on deep recurrent neural network and machine learning algorithms	2021	IoMT smart environment	Cyberattack detection
45	Cyber attack detection for internet of health things through federated deep learning technique	2024	Internet of Health Things	Cyberattack detection
46	Federated deep learning-driven cloud-IoT framework for real-time healthcare monitoring and privacy-preserving anomaly detection	2025	Cloud-IoT healthcare monitoring	Privacy-preserving anomaly detection
47	Real-time monitoring and anomaly detection in hospital IoT networks using machine learning	2023	Hospital IoT networks	Real-time anomaly detection
48	An RFE/Ridge-ML/DL based anomaly intrusion detection approach for securing IoMT system	2024	IoMT	Anomaly intrusion detection
49	Improving IoMT Cybersecurity through GRU-Based Adaptive Ensemble Learning	2025	IoMT	Adaptive ensemble intrusion detection
50	L2D2: A Novel LSTM Model for Multi-class Intrusion Detection Systems in the Era of IoMT	2025	IoMT	Multi-class intrusion detection
51	Deep Learning-Based Network Intrusion Detection System for Internet of Medical Things	2023	IoMT health monitoring	Multimodal intrusion detection
52	A Security Model Based on LightGBM and Transformer to Protect Healthcare Systems	2022	Healthcare systems	Hybrid intrusion and malware detection
53	Detecting Cyber Attacks in Healthcare IoT Systems	2024	Healthcare IoT	Cyberattack detection